

EFFECT OF FRETTING WEAR ON PRELOAD RELAXATION IN BOLTED COMPOSITE JOINTS: THEORY AND SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, preload relaxation behaviour of a composite joint under cyclic load was investigated by considering fretting wear in the assemble region (i.e., interfacial wear between metallic fasteners and joined composites) along with composite material degradation caused by fibre breakage and matrix cracking. Firstly, a generalized Archard's model which supplement influence of the change of wear rate considered localized slid and pressure was developed. The proposed theoretical model was implemented in ABAQUS synergistically using user subroutine UMEHMOTION and ALE (Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian) adaptive meshing technology. The fretting wear, manifested as reduces in surface height, was calculated by UMEHMOTION by adjusting mesh motion using ALE adaptive meshing method. On the other hand, material degradation is modelled with using UMAT by means of updating the stiffness of composite material over fatigue cycles. The numerically predicted results regarding preload relaxation of bolted joints subjected to tensile-tensile fatigue was verified by experimental investigation. The results showed that the developed model was able to accurately predict preload relaxation of bolted composite joints under different torques subjected to varied tensile fatigue load.

1. INTRODUCTION

Preload relaxation is a prevailing failure mode of bolted composite joints when subject to cyclic fatigue loading. The preload degradation mechanisms of the composite joints can be attributed to fibre breakage, matrix cracking, and interfacial fretting fatigue manifested as localized slid and wear in the assembled region [1].

Fig.1: Schematic illustrating preload relaxation considered fretting wear and fatigue damage.

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Material and specimen

In this paper, double lap joints which consisting of composite laminates and medium carbon steel plates were chosen. Specimen configuration is shown in fig2. The composite laminates were made from unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg tapes (Prepreg type: T300/7901) from Weihai Guangwei Carbon Fibre Co., Ltd., China. A vacuum pressing machine was used to cure the composite laminates containing 67% fibre by volume. Specimen layer sequence was set to $[-45^\circ/0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ with 2mm thickness. The clamp parts were also made from medium carbon steel and the size is 96 mm \times 38.1 mm \times 2 mm. The size of metal connectors which were the same as the composite materials were 96 mm \times 38.1 mm \times 2 mm. The metal parts were M6 GB5782 bolted and the composite material were M5 bolted.

Fig.2: Specimen configuration

2.2 Fatigue test

In order to avoid serious fatigue damage and deformation of the specimen hole, the maximum stress should less than 50% static strength, selected as 4KN and 6KN. Tensile fatigue load on the end of the composite composites performed sinusoidal wave at frequency of 10HZ. The fatigue tests were carried out on a 100KN electro-hydraulic servo fatigue machine. A high precision washer-type compression load cell was attached between the bolt head and the fixed plate to measure the real-time preloading as well as an extensometer was used to measure the deformation of bolt hole.

2.3 Experimental results

As Fig 3-4 described, preloading relaxation and hole deformation of composite joints over 500k cycles of cyclic loading was observed depending on the initial preload and applied external loads. Normalized preload parameter P is set to represent relaxation, $P=P(n)/P_0$, where P_0 is the initial bolt preload and $P(n)$ is the relaxed preload at cycle number n . It is observed that preloading occurred a significant decline which value reaches 15-20% at the beginning then stay steady decay during subsequent cycles. Deformation of hole also follow the same law that significant increase in initial cycles

then steady growth. It is observed that the magnitude of relaxation decreases with increasing initial preload and increases with increasing applied external loads.

Fig.3 Preload relaxation curves in fatigue test with various combined initial preloads and cyclic loads.

Fig.4 Hole-deformation for composite bolted joints in fatigue test with various combined initial preloads and cyclic loads.

On the other hand, Figs 5- 6 showed, the surface of the composite material was abruptly worn along the thickness direction after the test. Observed by the microscope, the contact surface appears furrow after wear.

Fig.5 surface of CFRP laminate after 500000 cycles in fatigue test.

Fig.6 microscope photographs of surface of CFRP laminate around the bolt hole; (a) initial surface, (b) wear surface

3. Theoretical method

Considered the relaxation mechanism of composite bolted joints, the multi-scale effects which consists of local fretting wear on contact surfaces and property degradation due to fatigue damage accumulation for composite material are investigated in this paper. FE simulations were conducted using ABAQUS software, and a summary of the methodology for fatigue damage model and fretting wear model was shown as flow chat in fig.7.

Fig.7 Methodology to numerically model the preload relaxation in composite joints.

3.1 Progressive fatigue damage model

This paper uses a three-dimensional model developed by Shokrieh [2] to predict the progressive fatigue damage of carbon/epoxy laminates in the bolted composite joints. This model describes the material property degradation considering applied stress and fatigue cycle and can be expressed as

$$R(n, \sigma, r) = \left[1 - \left(\frac{\log n - \log 0.25}{\log N_f - \log 0.25} \right)^\beta \right]^{1/\alpha} [R(0) - \sigma] + \sigma \quad (1)$$

$$E(n, \sigma, r) = \left[1 - \left(\frac{\log n - \log 0.25}{\log N_f - \log 0.25} \right)^\lambda \right]^{1/\gamma} \left[E(0) - \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon_f} \right] + \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon_f} \quad (2)$$

where $R(n, \sigma, r)$ denotes residual strength, $E(n, \sigma, r)$ denotes residual stiffness, $R(0)$ represents static strength, $E(0)$ represents static stiffness, ε_f signifies average strain to failure, α , β , λ and γ are experimental curve fitting parameters. Those parameters were used in the FEA to predict the preload relaxation, which are based on the Shokrieh's measured data (see Table 1-2).

Table1. The parameters for residual strength in the presented model.

Strength	α	β
X_t	10.03	0.473
X_c	49.06	0.25
Y_t	9.6287	0.1255

Y_c	67.36	0.0011
S_{12}	0.16	9.11
S_{13}	0.2	12.0

Table2. The parameters for residual stiffness in the presented model.

stiffness	λ	γ
E_{11}	14.57	0.3024
E_{22}	14.77	0.1155
G_{12}	0.7	11.0

Three-dimensional hashin criterion is used to determine composite material failure. Seven different failure modes for the unidirectional ply are considered, i.e., fibre tension, fibre compression, fibre-matrix shearing, matrix tension, matrix compression, normal tension and normal compression failure modes.

3.2 Wear model

When a bolted joint is applied with tightening torque, embedding occurs at the contact interface as a result of plastic flattening of rough asperities at the contact surfaces [3]. Due to micro reciprocating relative displacement between contact surfaces which are subject to pressure induced by the torque, fretting wear presents at the contact interface. According to Archard model[4], the relationship between local wear depth and sliding distance can be expressed as .

$$h = K_p p s \quad (3)$$

where h denotes wear depth, K_p represents wear coefficient, p signifies contact pressure and s is sliding distance.

Several authors have measured wear coefficient of epoxy composite which value is on the order of $10^{-8} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nmm}$. Freidrich et al. [5] investigate the effect of special filler on epoxy composite and found that wear coefficient is in range of $2 - 22 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nmm}$. Wan [6] focused on the friction and wear characteristics of carbon fibre-epoxy composite under lubricated sliding conditions against a (Friedrich, Zhang et al. 2005)medium-carbon steel counterface. The experimental result showed the wear rate range from $2-50 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nmm}$. In this simulation, wear coefficient is set to $2.5 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nmm}$.

In bolted joints, load transfer between assembled members is mainly achieved by friction. When contact surfaces become relatively smooth upon repeated friction, the contact performance of the interface tends to be stable.

3.3 Numerical simulation

Based on previous analysis, finite element method is used to model preload relaxation of bolted composite joints subject to tensile-tensile fatigue regarding interfacial fretting wear and material degradation. The fretting wear, manifested as reduces in surface height, is calculated by UMEHMOTION for ABAQUS according to Archard model and is modelled by adjusting mesh motion using ALE adaptive meshing method. On the other hand, material degradation is modelled by updating the stiffness of composite material over fatigue cycles using UMAT.

Fig.8 Synergistic implementation of user subroutine UMAT and UMESHMOTION in ABAQUS

4. Finite element analysis

4.1 FE model

In order to promote a more meaningful interpretation of the experimental, a 1/8 finite element model is established to analyze composite joints relaxation in ABAQUS. All models were developed using C3D8 solid elements. The contact interaction law of the plates, with either the opposite plates or washers, were modeled as surface-to surface contact pairs. Coefficients of friction (COF) were set to 0.2 for all contact surface, as verified by Thoppul et al. [7]. Symmetric boundaries were applied and ALE region is showed as figure.9 The analysis was executed in three parts. During the first part, the preload, ‘bolt load’ arithmetic in ABAQUS, was applied to the joint, and fix as current length. During the second part, the effect of wear considered relative large slip distance caused by assembly clearance was analyzed. The UMESHMOTION subroutine was imported different clearances measured by experiments. And the third part analyzed steady-state relaxation.

Fig.9 Finite element model.

4.2 Results

As fig.10 showed , the damage of composite under fatigue stress and wear around the hole is simulated effectively in ABAQUS.

Figure .11 shows the predicted preload relaxation for composite bolted joints under different cyclic loads. It is observed that for any external loading condition the bolt load relaxation decreases with increasing initial bolt preload and increasing external dynamic load increases the rate of relaxation. Finite element analysis show a reasonably good agreement with experiment results.

Damage around bolt hole				
Fretting wear				
Cycles	1	100000	250000	500000

Fig.10 Simulation of composite damage and wear in ABAQUS

Fig. 11 FEA predicted results for preload relaxation compared with testing data.

5. Conclusions

Experiments have been employed to study property degradation of composite material and preload relaxation of composite joints along with the effects of fretting wear. Numerical models consist of progressive degradation effect and sudden degradation caused by failure are used for simulating composite material fatigue performance. The proposed theoretical model was implemented in ABAQUS synergistically using user subroutine UMEHMOTION and UMAT. The numerically predicted results regarding preload relaxation of bolted joints subjected to tensile-tensile fatigue was verified by experimental investigation. The results showed that the developed model was able to accurately predict preload relaxation of bolted composite joints under different torques subjected to varied tensile fatigue load.

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